

Slicing Future Internet Infrastructures Round Table

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Abstract

This technical report presents the slides and additional technical information concerning the SFI2 project proposal, use cases and current status (<https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home>).

SFI2 presentation and technical discussion occurred during the 12o Future Internet Research and Experimentation Workshop (WPEIF) round-table, named "SFI2 - SLICING FUTURE INTERNET INFRASTRUCTURES," hold at the XXXIX Brazilian Symposium on Computer Networks and Distributed Systems, Uberlândia - MG August 21, 2021 (<https://www.sbrc2021.facom.ufu.br/en/calls/wpeif>).

Index Terms

Experimental Networks, Network Slicing, Slicing-as-a-Service, Multi-domain slicing, Machine Learning, Resource Orchestration, Resource Allocation.

1 ABSTRACT - ROUND TABLE PRESENTATION

Network slicing is a new research topic that allows the virtualization of multiple logical and physical networks to provide Network-as-a-Service (NaaS) for distinct use cases. Network slicing potentially allows customized deployment of service and tenant requirements such as complex multi-network configuration. In achieving that purpose, enablers like software-defined networking (SDN) and network function virtualization (NFV) are essential [1].

The SFI2 project has the goal of providing a single multi-domain and slice-based provisioning solution among these testbed infrastructures. SFI2 aims to simplify the creation of complex networks with minimum configuration effort based on the intelligent orchestration of multi-domain slicing, offering Slice-as-a-Service (SlaaS) for future Internet developers. The SFI2 rationale is based on the integration of distinct experimental facilities in Brazil (FIBRE [2], FUTEBOL [3], 5GINFIRE [4], FIWARE [5], NECOS [6] and CloudNEXT [7]), deployed across several administrative domains, using a standard slice definition focusing on the experimentation of advanced services and applications [1].

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2 ROUND-TABLE SLIDES

Fig. 1.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

-- > **SFI2 links:**

- * SFI2: <https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home>
- * Deliverables: <https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home/deliverables>

Fig. 2.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 3.

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Fig. 4.

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Fig. 5.

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Fig. 6.

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Fig. 8.

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Fig. 9.

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Fig. 10.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

- Use case 1 homepage: <https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home/sfi2-use-case-1-machine-learning-bas>

Fig. 11.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 12.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

Fig. 13.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 14.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 15.

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Fig. 16.

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Fig. 24.

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Fig. 25.

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Fig. 26.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Contextualização – Gerenciamento ciente de QoE

Devemos considerar o contexto do usuário!

Valores de QoS podem mudar:

- Usuário está vendo efetivamente o vídeo?
- Qual é o dispositivo empregado?

Como saber o QoE se a ISP não tem acesso ao dispositivo do usuário?

Fig. 27.

-- > ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:

Fig. 28.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 29.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 30.

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Fig. 31.

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Fig. 32.

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Fig. 33.

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Fig. 34.

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Fig. 35.

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Fig. 36.

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Fig. 37.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 38.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

SFI2 - Slicing Future Internet Infrastructures

MULTIINSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH PROJECT

Fig. 39.

-- > **SFI2 INSTITUTIONS:**

Fig. 40.

-- > **SFI2 FUNDING:**
SFI2 Project is funded by FAPESP - Project 2018/23097-3

Fig. 41.

-- > **SFI2 SUPPORT:**

RNP - Brazilian Educational and Research Network
FIBRE Network - Future Internet Brazilian Environment for Experimentation

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